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Cul2 activation in the human embryo at the 8-cell stage.

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Citations

1. Lingaraju, G.M., Bunker, R.D., Cavadini, S., Hess, D., Hassiepen, U., Renatus, M., Fischer, E.S. and Thomä, N.H., 2014. Crystal structure of the human COP9 signalosome. *Nature*, 512(7513), pp.161-165.